

www.arseam.com

ANALYSIS OF HEAT TRANSFER THROUGH DIFFERENT SHAPE FINS USING CFD TOOL

Praveen Yadav

M.Tech Student

RPS Group of Institutions, Balana,
Mahendergarh (HR) – 123109

Rajender Singh

Associate Professor

Department of Mechanical Engineering
RPS Group of Institutions, Balana,
Mahendergarh (HR) – 123109

Abstract:

This research presents the results of numerical study of heat transfer and pressure drop in a heat exchanger that is designed with different shape fins. The heat exchanger used for this research consists of a rectangular duct fitted with different shape fins (pin fins as well as thin plate fin), and is heated from the lower plate. The fin shape and the heat exchanger (HE) configuration were numerically studied to maximize the convective heat transfer rate and minimize the pressure drop across the heat exchanger & also along the heat sink. For analysis a three dimensional finite volume based numerical model using CFD tool ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 was used. The simulation applied to estimate convection heat transfer rate of fin surface and pressure drop in duct due to shape change at two different Reynolds number (Re 5000 & 50000) with different pin fins & a thin plate fin in turbulent forced convection conditions. Different fin configuration includes tear drop, elliptical & rectangular cross section fins along with a thin rectangular plate fin, all having constant total surface area and pin height ratio having different fin material has been studied. The data and conclusions of this study can be applied to the optimization of different heat exchangers which are used in industry. It can also be used in the design of Heat sink having internal fins, Charge air-cooler tubes with internal fins, vertical tubes & pipes & also for external fins of air cooled I.C engines, compressors, electric motors, turbine blade cooling, space industry. The results obtained from the different simulations shows that convective heat transfer rate increases with increase in Reynolds number. Hence turbulent flow conditions of ($Re=5000$) are applied for the first simulation over all fin configurations & results shows that thin rectangular plate fin dissipates maximum heat transfer rate & posses minimum pressure drop along duct geometry, this result also represents that under less turbulent forced conditions thin plate fin is better than pin fins. While at much higher Reynolds number ($Re=50000$) elliptical pin fins have the maximum heat transfer rate & even minimum pressure drop as compared to all pin fin configurations. The research work also shows that material having higher thermal conductivity posses higher convective heat transfer rate. Despite having the same total surface area thin rectangular plate fin has the minimum volume which is beneficial from weight point of view.

Key words: CFD, FLUENT, Simulation, Optimization, Turbulence

1. Introduction

In Industries the thermal or heating problem is more common than domestics. So, there has been a great demand for high performance, lightweight, compact & economical heat transfer components. Even the heat dissipation medium is not enough for transformer of average and high power, which require more elaborated methods of cooling and generated heat, must be removed effectively. The most popular enhancement is the fin. **Fins** are the extended surfaces which are used to enhance the rate of heat transfer dissipation from heated surfaces to air. To achieve better performance, conventionally, fins are added to plain tubes resulting in large external surface area and high heat transfer performance and smaller dimensions. The common fins used extensively to increase the rates of forced convection heat transfer from systems are rectangular & circular fins because such fins are simple and cheap, to manufacture.

Fin technology has shown its excellent characteristic in heat transfer in electronics cooling and it seems that it's time to use this technology in conventional heat exchangers used in industrial application. The usage of this technology in tubes will overcome the problems that other heat transfer enhancement tubes could not solve for long time, i.e. large pressure loss and low total heat transfer efficiency. Its unique finned structure greatly increases heat exchanging area both inside and outside the tube with dramatically reduced thickness of boundary layers. The pin-fin tubes are widely used in the company's products, especially in heat exchangers (boilers, radiators). Fins can either be long with H/D greater than about 10, or short with H/D on the order of unity. Considering the negligible radiation heat transfer from fin surface and one dimensional conduction through the fin, the energy balance on a thin differential element is: The rate of heat conduction into the element = rate of heat conduction out of element + rate of heat convection from the element surface.

In the present paper, a method has been suggested for optimizing tear drop pin-fin, elliptical pin-fin, thin rectangular plate fin & rectangular pin-fin based on CFD.

2. Introduction to CFD

Computational fluid dynamics, abbreviated as CFD, is the science of predicting fluid, heat & mass transfer, chemical reactions, and related phenomena by solving numerically the set of governing mathematical equations:

- Conservation of mass
- Conservation of momentum
- Conservation of species
- Effects of body forces

Computers are being used to do the calculations required to simulate the interaction of fluids with surfaces that are defined by boundary conditions, and initial conditions. The **Navier-Stokes** equations form the basis of all CFD problems. In case of CFD, the geometry of the problem is first made. Then the volume of the fluid is quantified into discrete and definite cells which may be referred as the mesh. Then the modelling equations are all set up, boundary conditions defined. The simulation is then done iteratively so that the solution converges to a point. CFD may be used for both steady state and transient state analysis

3. Problem Description & Solution Procedure

Fig 3.1 Experimental setup of forced convection

This research is based on the problem of optimization of heat transfer from different shape fins (Pin-fins as well as thin plate fin). Problem has three parts: 1. Base 2. Fin surface 3. Duct. Solid Fin surface is mounted on the base and it is established in the duct and Heat supplied to the fin base uniformly and it conducted through fin surface and convected to the air which is flowing into the duct. Air is supplied by the blower at suitable velocity based

on Reynolds No Most of the recent research has concentrated on rectangular & circular pin fins, probably because they are easy to manufacture but, cylinders with elliptic shaped cross section & thin plate fin have lower resistance to the flow and lower friction factor than the circular ones, as well as a higher surface wetted area that can increase the heat transfer. This is shown in the presented study.

3.1 Model Description

In this research, four models are considered. The heat exchanger domain consists of three connected channels: Entrance section, pin-fin section and exit section. The pin-fin section is composed of 6 solid pins that are attached to Base which is considered as heat source. Three different pin shapes are considered: tear drop shape, elliptical shape and rectangular shape. Other than these a thin plate fin along the whole Base length is also simulated. Three different pin-fin morphologies along with a thin rectangular plate fin were investigated in this primary study. The main geometrical dimensions that characterize the heat exchanger are the pin height (H), the diameter of the cylindrical portion of the pin (D), for rectangular pin-fin & plate fin this parameter is considered as fin width), for elliptical pin-fin the two dimensions along major & minor axes are considered as (A) & (B), for rectangular plate fin the plate length is considered as (L), pin spacing (Δ). The total surface area is same for all pin fins & plate fin. The entrance section of the heat exchanger is composed of a rectangular duct having 400mm as length, 50mm as width and 50mm as height. The pin fin section which consists of the base area is in the middle having the length of 100 mm. The total surface area can easily be calculated from the following formula:

Total surface area = areas of the top & bottom+ area of the side.

3.2 Fins' geometry

The details of different pin-fins' morphologies are as follows:

The total surface area of all the fin geometries (pin fins & plate fin) is maintained as 2551mm². H/D ratio is constant for all fin geometries as 4.

All the Models are designed & generated by using software ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 or even it can also be generated by using SOLIDWORKS software. After the geometry Boolean command is used to separate the solid body (fin & base/bottom wall) because it can't be a fluid. For less calculation & to mesh less, symmetry along (YZ-Plane) is created & geometry is generated.

3.2.1 Tear drop pin-fin

Its cross section consists of a circular leading edge and a triangular trailing edge. Having the triangular portion of the pin will help increase the wetted surface area of the heat exchanger leading to a major increase in the heat transfer and the efficiency. In addition, it delays the separation in comparison with the circular cross section, which helps decrease the friction factor and the flow resistance leading to a major decrease in the pressure loss. The diameter (D) of the circular portion is 5 mm; height of the triangular trailing edge is 5 mm. Pin fin height (H) is taken as 20 mm. The total surface area of the individual pin fin is taken as 425.16 mm². Six drop shape pin fins solid surfaces are mounted on the base which is in the middle of the rectangular duct section over a length of 100 mm. Heat supplied to the fin base uniformly and it conducted through fin surface and convected to the air which is flowing into the duct. Air is supplied by the blower at suitable velocity based on Reynolds No.

Fig 3.2 Drop-shaped pin-fin configurations

Fig 3.3 Computational domain of experimental setup

Tetrahedral meshing is generated & the element size is taken as 5 mm & relevance centre is made fine. Figure 3.4 shows the meshing of the complete geometry (solid as well as fluid).

Fig 3.4 Meshing of overall tear drop fin geometry with named selection

3.2.2 Elliptical pin-fin

The elliptical cross section of each fin having major & minor axis dimension (A)=7mm & (B)=4.92mm. Height (H) of the elliptical fin is 19.38mm. Total surface area of a single elliptical pin fin is 425.16mm². Total surface area of all elliptical pin fins is 2551mm². Each elliptical pin fin is separated by 11.6mm. H/B ratio is maintained constant as 4. Six elliptical shape pin fins solid surfaces are mounted on the base which is in the middle of the rectangular duct section over a length of 100 mm. Heat supplied to the fin base uniformly and it conducted through fin surface and convected to the air which is flowing into the duct. Air is supplied by the blower at suitable velocity based on Reynolds No.

Fig 3.5 Elliptical shaped pin-fin configurations

Fig 3.6 Computational domain of experimental setup of elliptical pin fin

Fig 3.7 Meshing of overall elliptical fin geometry with named selection

3.2.3 Thin Rectangular plate fin

A thin rectangular plate having thickness/width(D) 2.5mm only, having length(L) & height(H) as 100mm & 10mm respectively. H/D ratio is maintained constant as 4. Total surface area of the plate fin surface is 2551mm². Rectangular plate fin solid surface is mounted on the base which is in the middle of the rectangular duct section over a length of 100 mm. Heat supplied to the fin base uniformly and it conducted through fin surface and convected to the air which is flowing into the duct. Air is supplied by the blower at suitable velocity based on Reynolds No.

Fig 3.8 Thin rectangular plate fin symmetrical geometry

Fig 3.9 Computational domain of experimental setup for thin plate fin

Fig 3.10 Meshing of overall plate fin geometry with named selection

3.2.4 Rectangular pin-fin

The rectangular cross section of each fin having width (D) of 5mm,length 4.5mm, Height (H) of the rectangular fin is 20mm. Total surface area of a single rectangular pin fin is 425.16mm^2 . Total surface area of all rectangular pin fins is 2551mm^2 . Each rectangular pin fin is separated by 14.6mm. H/B ratio is maintained constant as 4. Six rectangular pin fins solid surfaces are mounted on the base which is in the middle of the rectangular duct section over a length of 100 mm. Heat supplied to the fin base uniformly and it conducted through fin surface and convected to the air which is flowing into the duct. Air is supplied by the blower at suitable velocity based on Reynolds No.

Fig 3.11 Rectangular shaped pin-fin configurations

Fig 3.12 Computational domain of experimental setup for thin plate fin

Fig 3.13 Meshing of overall rectangular fin geometry with named selection

Mesh (Grid) Generation and Nomenclature

Meshing is done to divide the domain (complete body) so that we can get a better result at each & every point. Named selection is given at required parts of the geometry so as to define the boundary conditions & to check the results at desired part of the geometry. For named selection inlet portion of the duct where velocity will be defined as Velocity-inlet, Outlet of the rectangular duct is named as Pressure-outlet, heated bottom source Where the temperature is to be defined is named as Base, fins surface area is named as Wall, Symmetric plane along YZ is named as Symmetry & remaining complete body except solid body as Fluid.

In the problem setup section, click on the energy equation, it is required for all the fluid flow & thermal energy problems. K-epsilon (2-eqn) model is selected because this model provides superior performance for flows involving rotation, boundary layers under strong adverse pressure gradients, separation & recirculation.

Same **boundary conditions & solution technique/method** as defined in 3.4 & 3.5 are applied to solve all the problems.

3.3 Boundary Condition

Inlet - The inlet air temperature will set to 290 K. The inlet velocity depends on the chosen Reynolds number which is 5000 at a velocity of 1.5 m/s. Reynolds number is needed to be defined when we are dealing with forced convection case. The hydraulic diameter is 50mm.

Outlet - The outlet boundary condition was set to out flow. The hydraulic diameter is 50mm.

Base/bottom wall - The bottom wall is kept at a constant temperature of 500 K. Since it is a rigid boundary the no slip condition was applied leading to a zero velocity in the 3 directions, $U_x=U_y=U_z=0$. Material of the bottom wall /Base is Nickel.

Fins - Convective heat transfer for the air is taken as $30\text{W/m}^2\text{-k}$ because this is the case of forced convection of gases. Material of the Pin-fins & Plate-fin is copper for one simulation & aluminium for other simulation to check for the better results of convective heat transfer because copper has better thermal conductivity & aluminium is light in weight. Free stream temperature is set at 290K.

3.4 Solution Technique (method)

All flows were specified as steady state and incompressible. The realizable k-e turbulence model with standard wall function was set for each model. The Segregated 3D solver with an implicit formulation was set to solve the model. Green gauss node based spatial discretization (meshing) is used because it is a case of tetrahedral meshing. Residual convergence criteria is selected as none. Initialization is done so that the residual (difference between values of iterations) can be stopped at last minimum value & number of iterations are defined to run calculations.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Introduction

Upon completion of all the test runs, several key performance indicators were examined to understand the heat transfer characteristics and trends for each pin-fin configuration with different Reynolds numbers. Analysis has been done on four tubes of same dimensions but having different fin configuration or fin profile with same fin height to width ratio. At first tear drop pin-fin in rectangular duct has been considered, after that elliptical pin-fin, thin rectangular plate fin & rectangular pin-fin results have been considered. Several checks were performed in order to verify the generated results. The contour plots for velocity, temperature, pressure & nusselt number alongwith XY plots of pressure & temperature variation were observed separately to ensure that the results

satisfy the boundary conditions. The total convective heat transfer of wall(fin) is computed in the result section. The result file is generated by Fluent upon completion of each run was carefully examined and analyzed.

4.2 Heat transfer

As previously stated, pin-fins have been introduced in the planar duct in order to enhance overall heat transfer performance. The pins improve heat transfer rate due to the addition of their own surface area, and also by increasing flow turbulence levels, thereby giving rise to better transport rates. In the current section, results for 5000 & 50000 Reynolds number are presented. It implies both are turbulent flow regime. To understand results we study Temperature based results in graphical mode, Velocity results, Pressure based result & total convective heat transfer rate of fin surface (wall).

4.2.1 Tear drop pin-fin duct geometry (Re=5000)

Fig 4.1 contours of static temperature on tear drop fin & heated base

Maximum temperature on the bottom of the Wall has reached to the same temperature of the Base which is 500k, it is 420K at a level .25mm above the bottom of the wall & then decreasing suddenly.

Inlet velocity is set as 1.5 m/s, it has increased to 2.10 m/s over & above the pin fin surface in the duct & about 1.85 m/s at the exit. The velocity is represented over the symmetric plane. Fig 4.2 shows the velocity distribution at the symmetric plane.

Fig 4.2 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Now the **primary problem** in fin designing which must be overcome is **low convective heat transfer rate**, so its most important point is to compute convection heat transfer rate from the Wall & for tear drop pin fin surface, the computed result displayed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
----- wall	-0.23663848
----- Net	-0.23663848

So, the total convective heat transfer rate by tear drop pin fins computed by ANSYS FLUENT software under defined boundary conditions is **-0.23663848 w**.

Another major problem is **large pressure loss** in the usage of this technology in the tubes, so it is important to find out the total pressure loss in the duct. Pressure drop is a term used to describe the differential pressure that fluid must overcome to flow through a system. Pressure drop is a result of resistance caused by friction (shear stress) or other forces (such as gravity) acting on a fluid. Total pressure is the pressure a fluid exerts as it is brought to a stop. X-Y Plot in fig 4.3, provides us the exact information about total pressure at the inlet, outlet section of the rectangular duct & the total pressure loss/drop. The figure 4.3 illustrates that the total pressure at the inlet of the duct is 2.60 pascal & the minimum total pressure at the outlet is 0.60 pascal, so the total pressure loss/drop in the rectangular duct is **2.00 pascal**. In most cases minimum pressure drop through a system is desirable, pressure drop can be minimised by removing the kinks, avoiding long hoses & by choosing optimum kink surface.

Fig 4.3 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

If the fin material is aluminium rather than copper in the pin-fin duct section then the total heat transfer by convection is **-0.23683263 w**.

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
----- wall	-0.23683263
----- Net	-0.23683263

The results shows that the fin material which has higher thermal conductivity has more heat dissipation by convection, despite the fact that aluminium is lighter in weight but due to higher thermal conductivity copper has higher heat dissipation rate by convection which comes out to be **-0.23663848 w**, hence copper is a better material for convective heat transfer rate as using fin material.

The purpose behind using 5000 Reynolds No. Is that in case of laminar flow using **Re** as 2000 the total heat tranfer by convection from the copper fin surface is **-0.2943198 w**, which shows that we should go for much higher Reynolds No.

5.2.2 Tear drop pin-fin duct geometry (Re=50000)

Here Inlet velocity is set as 15 m/s, it has increased to 19 m/s in pin fin section of the duct & about 16 m/s at the exit.The velocity is represented over the symmetric plane un figure 4.4

Fig 4.4 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Now the **primary problem** of **total convection heat transfer rate** as computed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 4 with **Re** 50000 for tear drop pin fin surface is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	-0.017224945
Net	-0.017224945

Fig 4.5 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

Total pressure at the inlet of duct is 198 pascal & minimum total pressure at the outlet is 70 pascal, so the **total pressure drop** in rectangular duct is **128 pascal**.

5.2.3 Elliptical pin-fin duct geometry (Re=5000)

Fig 4.6 contours of static temperature on elliptical pin fin & heated base

Maximum temperature on the bottom of the Wall(mainly by conduction) has reached to 452K, it is 333K at a level 1mm above the bottom of the wall & then decreasing suddenly. Inlet velocity of 1.5 m/s has increased to 2.15 m/s in the pin fin section in the duct & about 1.80 m/s at the exit. The velocity is represented over the symmetric plane in fig 4.7

Fig 4.7 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Convection heat transfer rate from the from elliptical pin fin surface(wall) , the computed result displayed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	-0.20287238
Net	-0.20287238

So, the total convective heat transfer rate by elliptical pin fins computed by ANSYS FLUENT software under defined boundary conditions is **-0.20287238 w**.

Higher **Nusselt number** represents higher heat dissipation by convection as compared to heat generated by conduction. Here at one elliptical pin fin the Nu has reached even upto 2530.

Fig 4.8 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

The figure 4.8 illustrates that the total pressure at the inlet of the duct is 2.70 pascal & the minimum total pressure at the outlet is 0.71 pascal, so the total pressure loss/drop in the rectangular duct is **1.99 pascal**. The reason is that in this configuration flow particles follow a smoother path line.

5.2.4 Elliptical pin-fin duct geometry (Re=50000)

For 50000 Reynolds No. Inlet velocity is set at 15 m/s, it has increased to 20 m/s over & above the pin fin surface in the duct & about 17 m/s at the exit. The velocity is represented over the symmetry.

Fig 4.9 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Total convection heat transfer rate as computed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 with **Re 50000** for elliptical pin fin surface is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	0.0016956513
Net	0.0016956513

The total convective heat transfer rate by tear drop pin fins computed by ANSYS FLUENT software under defined boundary conditions is **0.0016956513 w**. This is the maximum convective heat dissipation rate by any fin geometry among considered **Re**.

Fig 4.10 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

Total pressure at the inlet of duct is 206 pascal & minimum total pressure at the outlet is 79 pascal, so the total pressure drop in rectangular duct is **127 pascal**.

5.2.5 Thin rectangular plate fin duct geometry (Re=5000)

Maximum temperature on the bottom of the Wall has reached to a temperature of 400k, it is 375K at a level 1mm above the bottom of the wall & then decreasing linearly.

Fig 4.11 contours of static temperature on rectangular plate fin & heated base

For 5000 Reynolds No. Inlet velocity is set at 1.5 m/s, it has increased to 1.85 m/s in the pin fin section of the duct & remains same at the exit.

Fig 4.12 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Convection heat transfer rate from the thin rectangular plate fin surface(Wall), the computed result displayed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	-0.1416964
Net	-0.1416964

Hence, the total heat transfer rate by convection from thin rectangular plate fin computed by ANSYS FLUENT software under defined boundary conditions is **-0.1416964 w**.

At about 30 percent of plate fin area the **Nu** is around 200 or more, which is a good indication of convective heat transfer over conduction rate.

Fig 4.13 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

The total pressure at the inlet of the duct is 2.40 pascal & the minimum total pressure at the outlet is 0.80 pascal, so the total pressure loss/drop in the rectangular duct is **1.60 pascal**. It is the least pressure drop as compared to all pin fins.

5.2.6 Thin rectangular plate fin duct geometry (Re=50000)

For 50000 Reynolds No. Inlet velocity is set at 15 m/s, it has increased to 20 m/s over & above the pin fin surface in the duct & about 17 m/s at the exit.

Fig 4.14 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Total convection heat transfer rate as computed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 with **Re 50000** for thin rectangular plate fin surface is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	-0.022180453
Net	-0.022180453

The results of the total pressure as generated by figure 4.15 shows that the total pressure at the inlet of duct is 182 pascal & minimum total pressure at the outlet is 88 pascal, so the total pressure drop in rectangular duct is **94 pascal**. This is the minimum pressure drop for all considered configurations including thin plate fin & pin-fins at 50000 Re.

Fig 4.15 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

5.2.7 Rectangular pin-fin duct geometry (Re=5000)

Fig 4.16 contours of static temperature on rectangular pin-fin & heated base

Maximum temperature on the bottom of the Wall has reached to 440K, it is around 320K at a level 5mm above the bottom. Inlet velocity of 1.5 m/s has increased to 1.95 m/s in the pin fin section of the duct & is 1.80m/s at exit.

Fig 4.17 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

Convection heat transfer rate from the Wall of rectangular pin fin surface as computed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 for rectangular pin fins geometry is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	-0.30819158
Net	-0.30819158

So, the **total convective heat transfer rate** by rectangular pin fins computed by ANSYS FLUENT software under defined boundary conditions is **-0.30819158 w**.

Fig 4.18 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

The total pressure at the inlet of the duct is 2.60 pascal & the minimum total pressure at the outlet is 0.60 pascal, so the total pressure loss/drop in the rectangular duct is **2.00 pascal**. The total pressure drop of 2.00 pascal shown by rectangular pin fin is higher than elliptical pin fin case & rectangular plate fin section case.

5.2.8 Rectangular pin-fin duct geometry (Re=50000)

Fig 4.19 contours of velocity distribution over the symmetry

For 50000 Reynolds No. Inlet velocity is set at 15 m/s, it has increased to 20 m/s over & above the pin fin surface in the duct & about 17 m/s at the exit.

Total convection heat transfer rate as computed by ANSYS FLUENT 14.0 under the boundary conditions defined in chapter 3 with Re 50000 for elliptical pin fin surface is as follows:

Total Heat Transfer Rate	(w)
wall	-0.21099751
Net	-0.21099751

Fig 4.20 XY Plot representing total pressure at inlet & outlet section of duct

Total pressure at the inlet of duct is 200 pascal & minimum total pressure at the outlet is 61 pascal, so the total pressure drop in duct is **139 pascal**.

5. Conclusions

From the results the following conclusions may be drawn:

- As per the result discussion we can see for turbulent Flow at $Re= 5000$ Heat transfer rate of Tear drop pin fin is $-0.2366 w$, elliptical pin fin is $-0.2028 w$, thin rectangular plate fin is $-0.1416 w$ and rectangular pin fin $-0.30819 w$ so heat transfer rate is maximum for thin rectangular plate fin and minimum for rectangular pin fin. In case of pin fins maximum heat dissipation is from elliptical cross section pin fins. This result also shows that thin plate fin heat sinks & heat exchangers are better than pin fin ones at $5000 Re$. Different fin geometries in decreasing order of their heat transfer rate are as follows: Thin rectangular plate fin > Elliptical pin fin > Tear drop pin fin > Rectangular pin fin.
- As per the result discussion we can see for turbulent Flow at $Re= 50000$ Heat transfer rate of Tear drop pin fin is $-0.0172249 w$, elliptical pin fin is $0.00169565 w$, thin rectangular plate fin is $-0.02218 w$ and rectangular pin fin $-0.21099 w$ so heat transfer rate is maximum for elliptical pin fin and minimum for rectangular pin fin. This result also shows that pin fin geometries (elliptical & tear drop) heat sinks & heat exchangers are better than rectangular fin ones (thin plate & pinned both) at $50000 Re$. Different fin geometries in decreasing order of their heat transfer rate are as follows: Elliptical pin fin > Tear drop pin fin > Thin rectangular plate fin > Rectangular pin fin.
- Total heat transfer rate by convection at $5000 Re$ for tear drop pin fin shows that copper fins dissipates $-0.236638 w$ & aluminium fins dissipates $-0.236832 w$ at the same boundary conditions, it shows that the finned material of higher thermal conductivity is more effective as a fin material.
- For Turbulent Flow Pressure loss at $5000 Re$ of tear drop pin fin is 2.00 Pascal, elliptical pin fin 1.99 Pascal, thin rectangular plate fin 1.60 Pascal and rectangular pin fin 2.00 Pascal so Pressure loss is minimum for Thin rectangular plate fin and maximum for rectangular pin fin in the Duct. Different fin geometries in increasing order of total pressure loss through duct are: Thin rectangular plate fin < Elliptical pin fin < Tear drop pin fin = Rectangular pin fin.
- For Turbulent Flow Pressure loss at $50000 Re$ of tear drop pin fin is 128 Pascal, elliptical pin fin 127 Pascal, thin rectangular plate fin 94 Pascal and rectangular pin fin 139 Pascal so Pressure loss is minimum for Thin rectangular plate fin and maximum for rectangular pin fin in the Duct. Different fin geometries in increasing order of total pressure loss through duct are: Thin rectangular plate fin < Elliptical pin fin < Tear drop pin fin < Rectangular pin fin.

- f) With equal pin-fin surface area for all morphologies, the elliptical pins have the maximum volume which increases the weight. This is another factor that should be considered for optimization. Thin rectangular plate has the minimum weight, which is a benefit from weight point of view. The increasing order of different fin arrangements according to their weight: Thin rectangular plate fin < Tear drop pin fin < Rectangular pin fin < Circular pin fin < Elliptical pin fin.
- g) In case of laminar flow using Re as 2000 the total heat transfer by convection from the copper fin surface is - 0.2943198 w, convection heat transfer at 5000 Re in turbulent flow is -0.23683 w & at 50000 Re it is - 0.0172249 w. Turbulent flows can give rise to convective heat transfer rates which are much larger than those of laminar flows, and are caused by the manner in which the turbulent fluctuations increases mixing.
- h) Thin plate fin heat sinks possess the minimum pressure drop under all conditions.
- i) Out of all pin fins, elliptical pins showed best results, even better than tear drop shaped morphology.
- j) The overall work concludes that fins enhance heat transfer from a surface by exposing large surface area to convection. Under forced convection turbulent flow at 5000 Re thin rectangular plate fin is most effective. This also shows that under these conditions **thin plate fin** is better than **pin fins** while at much higher Reynolds number (Re=50000), the use of **elliptical pin fins** is justified to overcome the problems of low convection heat transfer rate & large pressure drop.

References

1. B. Moshfegh, R. Nyireddy, Comparing RANS Models for Flow and Thermal Analysis of Pin Fin Heat Sinks, 15th Australasian Fluid Mechanics Conference, the University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia 13-17 December 2004.
2. Christopher L. Chapman, Seri Lee, Bill L. Schmidt, Thermal Performance of an Elliptical Pin Fin Heat Sink, Tenth IEEE Semi-Ther MPFeb. 2000.
3. Jihed Boulares, Numerical and Experimental Study of The Performance of a Drop-Shaped Pin Fin Heat Exchanger, Master Research, NAVAL POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL Monterey, California, 2003.
4. Kröger, D.G, Performance characteristics of industrial finned tubes presented in dimensional form, Int. Journal of Mass and Heat Transfer, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 1119-1125, 1986
5. Mukesh Didwania, Gopal Krishan, Ravikant, Study and Analysis of Heat Transfer through Two Different Shape Fins using CFD Tool.
6. Myhren J.A., Holmberg S., Improving the thermal performance of ventilation radiator-the role of internal convective fins, International journal of heat and mass transfer, 2010, vol. 50, pg. 115-123
7. Nabati H., Mahmoudi J., Numerical Study of Thermal Performance of Different Pin-Fin Morphologies, 46th Conference on Simulation and Modeling (SIMS 2005), Trondheim, Norway, 2005
8. Rustum, I.M. and Soliman, H.M., Experimental investigation of laminar mixed convection in tubes with longitudinal fins, Journal of Heat Transfer, vol. 110, May, pp. 366-372, 1988.
9. Sanjay Kumar Sharma and Vikas Sharma, maximizing the heat transfer through fins using CFD Tool.
10. Sazali N., Experimental study of natural convection heat transfer in a vertical internally finned tube, 2009
11. Zhang, Y. and Faghri, A., Heat transfer enhancement in latent heat thermal energy storage system by using the internally finned tube, Int. Journal of Mass and Heat Transfer, vol. 39, no. 15, pp. 3165-3173, 1996.